

Artificial Empathy

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Abstract

Artificial empathy refers to the capacity of artificial agents—particularly social robots—to engage in interactions based on emotional communication that are interpreted as empathic by human users. While often treated as a simulation of human emotional capacities, the concept has evolved into a site of theoretical inquiry at the intersection of cognitive science and (embodied) AI, philosophy of mind, philosophy of technology, and ethics. Rather than interpreting empathy in terms of internal emotional states, emerging approaches reframe it as a relational, embodied, and distributed process. This entry explores the origins, conceptual shifts, debates, and implications of artificial empathy, with particular attention to its potential to reshape understandings of emotion, sociality, and human–machine interaction.

Keywords

artificial empathy; affective computing; affective coordination; affective robotics; cognitive robotics; generative AI; human–robot interaction; relational cognition; (machine) emotion; social robotics

1. Introduction

Although empathy has often been regarded as a characteristic of humans and other social animals, the design of technologies capable of simulating or eliciting empathic responses has transformed its theoretical meaning. The attempt to operationalize empathy in artificial systems raises foundational questions about its nature, scope, and the forms of embodiment or mediation through which it can emerge.

Artificial empathy does not “replicate” human emotional experience. Instead, it involves the construction of interactional dynamics in which machines are designed to activate affective dynamics in humans, sometimes based on detecting, responding to, and modulating human emotional states. This acknowledgment shifts the focus of the debate from empathy as a subjective internal state to empathy as situated, embodied, and co-regulated inter-individual dynamic. It challenges distinctions between genuine and simulated emotion and invites reflection on the social nature of human–robot relationships. Artificial empathy thus serves as a site for exploring how affective, cognitive, and ethical dimensions of mind are being redefined in technologically mediated interaction.

2. Background and Context

Since the beginning of social robotics at the end of the 1990s, robotic studies on artificial empathy were based on efforts to explore the operationalization of the notion of empathy in two main directions (Damiano et al., 2015). The first concerned the modeling of emotional and empathic processes observed in humans and social animals, as in affective developmental robotics, where research investigates the sequential emergence of empathic capacities through interaction (e.g., Asada, 2015; Cañamero, 2005; Parisi, 2004; Pfeifer & Scheier, 1999; Ziemke & Lowe, 2009). The second focused on functional applications in social and assistive robotics, such as Paro, KASPAR, or Aibo, which do not attempt to reproduce human or animal emotional mechanisms, but use affective cues to facilitate interaction and the recognition of a robot’s “social presence” (e.g., Biocca et al., 2003; Belpaeme et al., 2012; Dautenhahn et al., 2009; Feil-Seifer, Matarić, 2011; Shibata, 2012).

Building on insights from both directions, philosophical efforts to define artificial empathy in the field of social robotics developed insights from cybernetic, autopoietic, and enactive epistemology to delineate it as a form of social and, specifically, affective coordination, enacted

in real-time interaction, rather than as an internal mechanism to be replicated (e.g., Dumouchel & Damiano, 2017; Damiano & Dumouchel, 2020, 2024, 2025).

Recent related contributions highlight the “ontological ambiguity” of artificial empathy, describing it as a liminal phenomenon between simulation and affective presence (Malinowska, 2021, 2022). These analyses reinforce the view that artificial empathy cannot be reduced to deception or mimicry, but must be examined as a mode of human-robot (or socio-technological) relationality that destabilizes distinctions between subject and object, or between internal state and external behavior (Damiano et al., 2015).

Today, artificial empathy is a key concept at the crossroads of philosophy of science and technology, philosophical psychology, robot ethics, cognitive and affective science. Its developments reflect a broader shift toward relational and processual understandings of mind, cognition, and intersubjectivity (e.g., Varela et al., 1991, Gallese, 2007; Damiano, 2021).

3. Current Debates

What counts as empathy in human-robot interaction? Must it be grounded in affective experience? Can it be ethically designed, and under what conditions? These issues, generated by the relevance of artificial empathy in the construction of robots’ social presence, have given rise to theoretical, ethical, and legal challenges. Rather than forming a unified field, discussions around artificial empathy have crystallized into distinct positions concerning the nature, legitimacy, and implications of emotionally responsive robotic agents. The following four axes intend to summarize key dimensions of this evolving discourse.

3.1 Authenticity and Simulation

A first axis concerns the authenticity of artificial emotional expression. Early debates questioned whether machines that simulate empathy can genuinely participate in affective understanding or whether such displays are necessarily deceptive—an issue raised in moral and psychological critiques of robotic care (e.g., Sparrow, 2002; Turkle, 2011; Sharkey & Sharkey, 2012). Some authors argue that authenticity in human–robot interaction should be judged pragmatically by the quality of engagement it supports—a view discussed and problematized by Coeckelbergh (2015) through a phenomenological analysis of care, which highlights how apparently authentic engagement can conceal forms of alienation inherent in modern technological mediation. This discussion remains central to evaluations of empathy in artificial systems, revealing a tension between simulation as manipulation and simulation as mediation.

3.2 Affective Design and Anthropomorphism

A second axis focuses on affective design—the expressive and behavioral features that elicit empathic responses. Work in social robotics shows that even minimal cues such as motion, gaze, or vocal tone can trigger anthropomorphic projection, shaping users’ sense of “being with another” (e.g., Fong et al., 2007; García-Corretjer et al., 2023). While these cues can support therapeutic, educational, and self-developmental uses (Chin et al., 2023), they also raise questions about manipulation and consent, since designers can intentionally craft emotional effects (e.g., van Wylsberghe, 2016). Debates link this issue to research on anthropomorphism and embodiment in social robots (Darling, 2015; Kühne et al., 2024; Yang, Xie, 2024) and to analyses of affective computing that explore how emotional displays can both foster cooperation and commodify affect. The resulting discussion contrasts instrumental uses of empathy, where emotion functions as a design tool, with relational ones that aim to sustain meaningful coordination between humans and machines (e.g., Gemeinboeck, Saunders, 2022; Sousa, Ferreira, 2024).

3.3 Empathy, Trust, and Moral Agency

A third axis examines empathy in relation to trust and moral status. Attributing empathic capacities to robots affects how users evaluate reliability, responsibility, and moral considerability. Studies of domestic and assistive robots have distinguished between functional trust in developers and regulators and moralized trust projected onto the robots themselves (e.g., Cominelli et al., 2021; Sweeney, 2023). Recent studies highlight how empathic cues influence users' expectations of sincerity and benevolence, shaping perceived trustworthiness and social credibility (e.g., Safdari, 2025).

Analyses of human–robot friendship and deception suggest that trust in empathic machines depends less on internal emotion than on relational transparency—the visibility of a system's capacities, limits, and intentions in interaction (e.g., Danaher, 2019, 2020).

These intertwined debates show that empathy in robots functions not only as a trigger of emotional engagement but also as a moral interface: a way of organizing trust, responsibility, and recognition within hybrid human–machine systems.

3.4 Generative AI and Emerging Challenges

A fourth and rapidly evolving axis concerns the integration of generative artificial intelligence into socially interactive robots. The use of large language models (LLMs) extends linguistic and expressive flexibility but also revives concerns about illusion and isolation (Obrenovic et al., 2025). Research shows that while LLM-based robots can produce highly adaptive dialogues, they may encourage dyadic loops that narrow social experience (Kim et al., 2024). Some analyses warn that such systems risk becoming “eloquent but socially hollow agents” (Bender et al., 2021). Current work explores relation-first design, embedding language models in multi-party, embodied contexts where gesture, gaze, and rhythm complement speech (Wang et al., 2024). At the same time, studies of AI deception emphasize transparency by design to counter misleading outputs (Park et al., 2024). These debates increasingly refer to social sustainability—the capacity of technological systems to preserve and enrich human bonds. Whether generative social robots will enhance cooperation or reinforce commodified forms of interaction remains an open question.

4. Possibilities

The emergence of artificial empathy is expanding the capacities of machines and transforming the conceptual frameworks through which psychology, philosophy, anthropology, sociology and ethics understand emotion, relation, and cognition. As empathic capabilities are engineered into artificial agents, the concept of empathy itself becomes exposed to redefinition.

This shift is intensified by current developments in AI. The convergence between generative AI and (social) robotics, while still evolving, appears likely to alter the social environments in which humans live, care, and communicate. Such changes affect how relational cues are interpreted, how vulnerability is distributed, and how affective norms are redefined. These transformations call for new frameworks able to describe hybrid forms of subjectivity and interaction.

In this evolving landscape, artificial empathy functions as a heuristic catalyst. It prompts reflection on the conditions under which empathy is attributed or recognized, on the role of embodiment in emotional understanding, and on the ethical implications of affective asymmetry. Rather than asking whether machines can feel, artificial empathy raises a broader question: what does it mean to feel, to relate, to be affected—when these processes are no longer involving exclusively humans and social animals?

5. Outlook

Artificial empathy is not merely a feature of emerging (robotic) technologies; it is a conceptual rupture that invites a reassessment of foundational assumptions about emotion, cognition, and relational life. As artificial agents increasingly participate in affective dynamics once considered specific to humans and other social animals, scientific inquiry—psychological and philosophical inquiry *in primis*—are compelled to respond. Rather than resolving whether machines can truly feel, artificial empathy exposes the fragility of this very question. Its significance lies in how it forces us to rethink the categories through which we define empathy, sociality, and the human—categories that may no longer hold in the ecologies we are beginning to inhabit.

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